

A PROPOSAL FOR DECREASING THE COST OF IELTS AND SUPPLYING EDUCATIONAL SETTINGS WITH QUALITY TESTS

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Abstract: The primary purpose of this paper is to propose a grand proposal. Almost in all countries, it is very costly participating in an IELTS because of its high acceptance rate in all international and national educational settings. With the help of this proposal, international test assessors are changed with national assessors to cut the cost of the test which is almost equal to an educated school teacher’s salary. National assessors are not only educated how to assess test takers’ skills but also how to create international tests to supply national schools and universities with tests based on international test making criteria.

Key vocabulary: IELTS, international language proficiency tests, international testing standards, test takers, test givers, test assessors.

Part 1. Summary of Proposal.

Language planning and Policy gave opportunity to write about our own proposals which brings changes to our society. As DJ Kaiser (2018) mentioned it is one of the means of improving language instruction, problem solving ability and increasing teacher agency. To find solution for one of the challenges in our society, I have chosen Grand proposal which proposes more opportunities in the field of testing English language proficiency in Uzbekistan. This chosen proposal is a chance for applicants who are going to achieve English language proficiency certificate in their own hometown with inexpensive payment. Before achieving MA, I also had to pursue IELTS certificate. This is why I went to Tashkent city from Tashkent region (Almalyk) which takes a half and an hour to get here, and I made payment (a million and seven hundred sum) which was equal to my monthly salary. International tests like TOEFL, IELTS are assessed by foreign test givers only in eight cities in Uzbekistan. If Uzbek students with master degree and university English language teachers are practiced by special foreign test trainers on how to assess test takers language proficiency according to International English Tests, there will not be necessity for assessment by native English assessors. Additionally, the evaluation does not consume much money, and there is not much excitement of applicants because of Uzbek assessors. Actually, Uzbek test givers use International English tests organized by international specialists, yet assessing productive and receptive skills according to holistic and analytic scales are carried out by them.

After December, 2012, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued Decree “On further enhancement of measures on foreign language learning system” to learn English and receiving language proficiency certificates to enter Uzbek and abroad universities (G. Azizova, 2015, p. 27). Of course, if applicants achieve suitable level from International English proficiency tests, they may not participate in entrance exams for entering universities from English language in Uzbekistan. In addition, certificates are not achieved only for studying purposes but there are working and other purposes. My proposal is going to change foreign assessors with future Uzbek assessors around Uzbekistan which helps applicants not to spent more energy to go to existing test centers which are far from their hometown and not to make more expenditure. It is fact that there are eight locations across Uzbekistan where exist international English language proficiency test centers: Tashkent, Namangan, Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, Karshi and Urgench with eight test dates in a month. First, for this purpose exact number of master degree students and university teachers are chosen according to some requirements. They should have minimum 8 band from International English Language Testing System (IELTS) or C1 from Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) and their major should connect with English language as well. After choosing exact number of participants, they are taught and practiced only in capital city during a year, then from the next year, the process is continued in other cities around Uzbekistan. It means that every region will have training centers for test givers and the places will have special departments or building for applicants’ test taking. Furthermore, the participants learn the ways of creating suitable tests for university and schools since there are some teachers cannot create perfect tests and even, do not know the principles of tests, as a result, they use existing tests blindly. Every month, after completing any part of testing they should show their gained knowledge in practice like choosing any test taker and giving one of the sample tests and assessing them. The checked and calculated results of test takers are checked by international trainers whether they are ready or not. At the end, they will achieve rights to give and to check the tests takers’ results.

Moreover this proposal aims at carrying out several goals and objectives. General goals are to increase amount of world standard test givers and assessors around Uzbekistan to improve quality of existing tests in universities or schools or create suitable ones by the help of the members. Because after learning test specifications, principles and other features, they get know all information which shows ways for creating and developing tests. Next one is reducing amount of money which is paid for the tests by applicants is one of essential goals as well.

Objectives work for carrying out successful management of goals. The trainers should raise participants’ awareness about the means of assessing test results

according to assessment criterions and enable participants how to create tests which can be used at schools and universities (it is the good chance to create sufficient tests since most teachers are using their tests which do not supply international testing standards). For effective management of the proposal, objectives and goals should be required to meet needs and national level goals (reducing payment, supplying society with Uzbek assessors) and local objectives (teaching how to evaluate students, creating tests etc.) must be well-organized beforehand.

Part 2. Annotated Bibliography

1. Azizova, G. (2014). Uzbekistan government policy towards teaching English language. (25-28)

For proving my points with facts about background information of Uzbekistan, the laws which are given in the article are very effective.

2. Brown, (2001). Assessment concepts and issues. (pp.1-23)

With the help of the article I can clarify types of assessment issues and use for the proposal that members should be aware of them while evaluating results. In addition it is handfull for creating and modifying types of tests for schools and universities since it gives data about test types as well.

3. Brown, (2001). Principles of language assessment. (pp. 25-51).

The necessity for this article is that it informs about the existing tests' measurement according to the language assessment at universities and schools for the participants of the proposal.

4. Kaiser, DJ. (2018). Growing your own onion: Teachers as writers of Language Planning and Policy. (pp.1-30)

This article helps organize the structure of writing language planning and policy proposal and gives special advices how to write every part of the proposal with examples.

5. Linton, A. (2009). Language politics and policy in the United States: implications for immigration debate.

The article improves my understanding about language policy and I use the policy for carrying out my proposal and showing the role of policy also one of the proposals' priorities.

6. Richard, B, Kheng, C, & Baldauf, Jr. (2008). Micro language planning. (pp.936-948).

While planning proposal usage of micro and macro planning is essential parts which help to achieve goals and objectives.

7. Robert, B. Kaplan. (2008). Macro language planning. (924-933).

My proposal is planned according to a developing country level, this is why it utilizes macro language planning rules.

References:

1. Mirzayeva, M. U. "THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIMEDIA MATERIALS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES. THE ANALYSIS OF ARTICLE." Академические исследования в современной науке 3.10 (2024): 129-132.
2. Mirzayeva, Mamura. "LANGUAGE ANXIETY IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AMONG TEENAGERS. DEVELOPMENT OF ACTIVE LEARNING BY POSITIVE ASPECTS OF ANXIETY IN SPEAKING TASKS AMONG ADOLESCENTS." Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования 1.24 (2022): 150-156.
3. Mirzayeva, Mamura. "IMPORTANCE OF CASE STUDY IN TEACHING EFL." Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика 1.24 (2022): 574-576.
4. Mamura, Mirzayeva, and Ruzikulova Gulirukhsor. "INTERLANGUAGE ERRORS IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AMONG LEARNERS." Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali 1.10 (2022): 166-170.